

Reproducing: Do Simpler Statistical Methods Perform Better in Multivariate Long Sequence Time-Series Forecasting?

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The goal is to reproduce the results of the paper "Do Simpler Statistical Methods Perform Better in Multivariate Long Sequence Time-Series Forecasting?". Without having the original code at disposal, it is not possible to reproduce the exact results for the different data sets. The implementation neither match the outlined intention of the article nor do the described models in the paper perfectly coincide with that. Based on our implementation of the intended setup we cannot conclude that simpler approaches perform better than recent deep learning methods.

CCS Concepts: • **Mathematics of computing** → **Probability and statistics**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Time-series forecasting; deep learning; statistical methods

1 INTRODUCTION

Replication is a fundamental tenet of science. The awareness for reproducibility of research outcomes increased in the past years and it is increasingly viewed as a minimum standard that all scientists should strive toward [1]. This article contributes to that field of research by trying to reproduce the outcome of the research paper "Do Simpler Statistical Methods Perform Better in Multivariate Long Sequence Time-Series Forecasting?" [3]¹. The authors benchmark large deep learning frameworks such as Informer and SCINet for multivariate long sequence time-series forecasting with simpler statistical methods like linear regression and SNaive.

In our study we try to reproduce the outcome and conclusion of the original paper. This article is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an overview about the fundamentals and intention of the original paper. In Section 3 we describe our criticism of the experiment, with special focus on the evaluation metrics and the considered models. Section 4 outlines the outcome of our reproduced results and compares it to the original paper and the results of the best performing complex models. The last Section concerns the conclusion of the reproducibility.

2 FUNDAMENTALS OF THE ORIGINAL PAPER

The research paper follows the general structure for a published article. At first an introduction to the topic is provided including an outline of the contribution of the paper. Following related research work is briefly discussed mainly dealing with the more complex approaches for multivariate long sequence time-series forecasting (MLSTF). Subsequently the simpler statistical methods, i.e., linear regression and SNaive, are described with the demonstration that the linear regression owns a lower-order upper bound of error than non-linear model with the same input length. SNaive is considered in the article because it is a simple method to utilize the last same-season observations. Experimental details like data sets, evaluation matrix, and the results are provided afterwards. The final section then concludes that the simpler statistical methods were able to achieve better results than the recent deep learning methods.

¹Here, we refer to that article usually with "original paper".

In this study here the focus of the authors was to confirm the numbers and findings reported in the paper and to uncover possible inconsistencies and therefore challenge the conclusions drawn. The review of the soundness of the simpler methodologies as an alternative for the more complex approaches for MLSTF was out of scope.

2.1 Research Question

Although not specifically stated in the article the hypothesis of the research can be summarized as follows: "Simpler statistical methods, like linear regression and SNaive, perform better in multivariate long sequence time-series forecasting than recent deep learning methods". We are not completely sure about the original intention of the paper. Although the article writes about multivariate time-series forecasting, in the linear regression and SNaive only single time-series are considered in the calibration to make predictions of the very same time-series for a long sequence. Usually, multivariate analysis deals with looking at many different inputs together to make predictions.

In order to verify the hypothesis of the original paper a lemma is defined and additionally an experiment across eight data sets is conducted. The outcome of the lemma is that "the error of the non-linear model (e.g., deep learning methods) would exceed the linear regression, because it could be approximated as high-order polynomial leading to high error in large n case." Hao et al. [3] then conclude that linear regression is worth firstly considering for MLSTF. Furthermore, from the experiment across the eight data sets they conclude that both statistical methods were able to achieve better results than the recent deep learning methods.

The two simple methods for MLSTF are shortly described in the original paper. The linear regression [3] is formulated as follows:

$$\hat{x}_{j,n+i} = \theta_{j,1}x_{j,1} + \dots + \theta_{j,n}x_{j,n}, \quad (i = 1, \dots, h, j = 1, \dots, d), \quad (1)$$

$$\hat{X}_{n+i} = (\hat{x}_{1,n+i}, \dots, \hat{x}_{d,n+i})^T, \quad (i = 1, \dots, h) \quad (2)$$

where $\theta_{j,n}$ is parameters to be learned and $x_{j,1}, \dots, x_{j,n}$ is the j -th dimension of $X_{d \times n}$. The SNaive based forecasts equal to last known observation from the same season is defined as:

$$\hat{X}_{n+1} = X_{n+1-c}, \quad (i = 1, \dots, h), \quad (3)$$

where c is the seasonal period. We faced some challenges in understanding the model formulation, especially for the linear regression. In [3] the linear regression is formalized without an intercept, but in the original implementation² an intercept is used.³ Furthermore, the notation of the models was not consistent and therefore difficult to comprehend. Scalar values were mixed with vectors (compare formula 17 in [3]) and some indices were wrongly used (compare Equation (1), where all forecasts $i = 1, \dots, h$ are calculated on the same input as all $\theta_{j,n}$ and $x_{j,n}$ are the same).

For the evaluation of the prediction performance of the complex and simple methods the mean absolute error and the mean square error are considered. In both cases the z-score normalization is applied. The normalization is not based on the full train time series but only data up to a cut-point N_0 is considered. For one data set this point is defined as 0.75N (where N is the total length of train sample) and for all others it is set to 0.875N. No explanation is provided about this non-standard normalization split. We believe that this untypical treatment is done to be in line with a theoretical split of the training data into train and validation set, where the train set would consider the first 70% of total data and the validation set the next 10%, i.e., 70% / 80% = 0.875.

²The original Python code was only provided for the linear regression. No code snippet was available for the SNaive implementation.

³Running the original code without intercept impacts the outcome for MAE and MSE only slightly, approximately +-10%.

2.2 Data

Along with part of the implementation code we received almost all data sets used in the original paper. Despite that the data sets considered in the experiment are in general available using the original research papers that are cited in [3] for their benchmark exercise. No additional data pre-processing (apart from the above mentioned standardization) or manipulation was done.

3 CRITICISM OF THE EXPERIMENT

A couple of maybe minor shortcomings of the original paper were already mentioned in Section 2. In the following we focus on two major weaknesses of the paper, one related to the evaluation metric and another one related to the simple models.

3.1 Evaluation Metrics

In order to validate the hypothesis of the paper the mean squared error (MSE) and mean absolute error (MAE) is used to compare to the previously published machine learning models. This is mainly because these are the values published for the baseline models. In the original sources for the baseline models Liu et al. [4], Wu et al. [5] and Zhou et al. [6] the exact definition of these metrics is missing. However, this is a crucial information since the standard definition for MSE and MAE are not suitable for a multivariate prediction. Actually, a reference in Liu et al. [4] to Hyndman et al. [2] suggests, that the baseline models are compared on the mean squared scaled error and mean absolute scaled error. The scaled error q_t and the metrics are defined as follows:

$$q_t = \frac{e_t}{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=2}^n |Y_i - Y_{i-1}|}, \quad (4)$$

$$\text{MSSE} = \text{mean}(q_t^2), \quad (5)$$

$$\text{MASE} = \text{mean}(|q_t|). \quad (6)$$

The evaluation metrics in [3] for the simpler methods is based on:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{Hd} \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{j=1}^H \left(\frac{X_{ij} - \mu_i}{\sigma_i} - \hat{X}_{ij} \right)^2, \quad (7)$$

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{Hd} \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{j=1}^H \left| \frac{X_{ij} - \mu_i}{\sigma_i} - \hat{X}_{ij} \right|. \quad (8)$$

Clearly the metrics used for the baseline models in [4] and the simple models differ. Hence, the comparison based on these metrics cannot be done. Nevertheless, Liu et al. [4], Wu et al. [5] and Zhou et al. [6] also computed the MSE and MAE values for which the comparison can be made.

In the computation of the evaluation metrics in the original code we noticed that for each prediction point in time more than one value is computed and considered in the evaluation metrics. The implementation in the original code is set up in a way that a loop over each time point in the test set is applied (i.e., $n+1$, $n+2$) and in each time point the whole forecasting period (e.g., $h = 24$) is calculated. In that way several forecasts for a specific time point in the test set exists and the average of that is considered in the evaluation metrics.

In terms of evaluation metrics, we believe that the uncertainty around the predictions, especially for the very large prediction horizons, should be included in the comparison of the models. In the original paper no confidence interval around the forecasts is provided and neither is it discussed in the paper as a limitation of the study.

As described above, the notation in Equation (7) and (8) is sloppy, as the results of the formulas are vectors and not scalars. Additionally, the treatment of normalization is unusual as it is not based on the full training set but only a fraction.

3.2 Considered Models

The idea in the multivariate forecasting is to consider multiple time-dependent variables. In general, multivariate time series analysis in this context is used to model and explain interdependencies and co-movements among the variables. In the multivariate analysis — the assumption is that the time-dependent variables not only depend on their past values but also show dependency between them. The linear regression and SNaive approaches applied in the original paper focus on forecasting the different time series based on the respective past values of the single time series only, i.e., not taking the multivariate dimension into account.

In summary, it can be said, that while the approach seems similar to fitting an autoregressive (AR) model, the implemented approach is certainly different. When fitting an AR model usually it is taken into account if the data is stationary and the predictions for horizons > 1 are calculated recursively. Another shortcoming is related to the z-score normalization. Applying a normalization on a time series with significant trend, will lead to poor prediction forecasts, because the values used in the test set are (due to the trend) outside of the normalization range of the test data. This issue of having values outside the normalization range is applicable to the linear regression and SNaive approach.

For the SNaive approach the seasonality pattern is important (e.g., hourly, weekly, quarterly). Although, the value of the seasonality parameter is given in the article no explanation is given, how the authors derived this value.

4 REPRODUCING EXPERIMENT

Without (part of) the original code it would not have been possible for us to reproduce the values for linear regression given in Tables 1, 2, and 3 of the original article. That is partially because of discrepancies between the paper and the code (e.g., intercept, several forecasts for one time point), but rather due to different understanding of the intention of the paper (see discussion in Section 3.2). Using the original code that we had available for the linear regression and the provided data sets, we received (almost) identical values as given in the original article. For a few cases the values are not identical and we believe that these are partially typos in the paper (e.g., 2.168 instead of 2.158), but for some others it is not clear where the difference originate from (e.g., 2.233 instead of 2.241).

The results of the more complex models (i.e., deep learning) we did not reproduce, but we verified the values stated in the Tables 1, 2, and 3 of the original article. Most of the values coincide with the respective initial source, but again a few values are different. Looking into the details we believe that some of the wrong values are from previous versions of the respective initial source and not from the final published versions.

Dataset		ETTh1					ETTh2					ETTM1					ECL				
Horizon	Metric	24	48	168	336	720	24	48	168	336	720	24	48	96	288	672	48	168	336	720	960
Reprod. Snaive	MSE	1.666	1.891	1.745	1.705	1.819	1.335	1.241	0.798	0.646	0.752	1.413	1.043	1.027	0.532	0.568	1.177	0.827	0.748	0.590	0.533
	MAE	0.891	0.941	0.891	0.877	0.929	0.794	0.758	0.593	0.541	0.596	0.830	0.701	0.643	0.469	0.493	0.656	0.520	0.497	0.431	0.416
Reprod. Linear	MSE	1.473	1.423	1.300	1.428	1.472	0.773	0.437	0.365	0.380	0.407	0.689	0.436	0.359	0.322	0.353	0.330	0.515	0.447	0.375	0.352
	MAE	0.835	0.799	0.747	0.815	0.837	0.570	0.433	0.420	0.428	0.447	0.516	0.400	0.367	0.362	0.410	0.330	0.401	0.378	0.357	0.361
SNaive	MSE	0.424	0.465	0.656	0.683	0.650	0.266	0.322	0.578	0.567	0.550	0.168	0.168	0.188	0.225	0.282	0.212	0.212	0.212	0.228	0.267
	MAE	0.389	0.407	0.509	0.520	0.518	0.304	0.339	0.483	0.491	0.488	0.269	0.269	0.287	0.315	0.353	0.278	0.278	0.279	0.295	0.325
Linear	MSE	0.305	0.341	0.404	0.434	0.490	0.166	0.218	0.323	0.386	0.665	0.090	0.121	0.162	0.261	0.364	0.116	0.145	0.163	0.194	0.212
	MAE	0.357	0.379	0.422	0.445	0.501	0.261	0.299	0.374	0.419	0.549	0.185	0.219	0.253	0.325	0.394	0.213	0.240	0.260	0.291	0.308

Table 1. Comparison on ETTh1, ETTh2, ETTM1, and ECL

A comparison between the values from the original paper and our independent implementation for the different data sets is given in Tables 1 and 2. Here, we need to state clearly that we implemented a version different from the original code. Our implementation is based on our understanding of the intention of that study and the

corrected evaluation metric. As visible the results show severe discrepancies, which was to be expected. In almost all the cases our reproduced values are higher (e.g., for Linear and Exchange that is not always the case).

Dataset		WTH					Weather					ILI				Exchange			
Horizon		24	48	168	336	720	96	192	336	720	24	36	48	60	96	192	336	720	
Reprod. Snaive	MSE	1.845	1.556	1.190	1.110	1.150	0.590	0.447	0.483	0.509	5.800	5.859	6.133	5.926	0.614	0.311	0.372	0.857	
	MAE	1.012	0.912	0.762	0.745	0.759	0.445	0.377	0.396	0.424	1.660	1.692	1.736	1.726	0.481	0.359	0.426	0.698	
Reprod. Linear	MSE	0.892	0.748	0.847	0.697	0.753	0.240	0.228	0.243	0.295	4.493	4.113	4.446	5.059	0.162	0.191	0.291	0.589	
	MAE	0.657	0.621	0.666	0.627	0.664	0.259	0.273	0.306	0.353	1.484	1.422	1.490	1.548	0.246	0.291	0.390	0.596	
SNaive	MSE	0.599	0.698	0.848	0.908	0.960	0.317	0.343	0.383	0.443	2.564	2.266	2.142	1.917	0.081	0.167	0.306	0.810	
	MAE	0.468	0.525	0.608	0.642	0.674	0.288	0.305	0.331	0.370	1.004	0.957	0.941	0.939	0.196	0.289	0.398	0.676	
Linear	MSE	0.323	0.391	0.500	0.543	0.602	0.139	0.181	0.229	0.295	2.168	2.233	2.277	2.353	0.082	0.166	0.282	0.576	
	MAE	0.361	0.420	0.504	0.534	0.572	0.200	0.244	0.288	0.341	0.970	1.015	1.040	1.067	0.200	0.292	0.395	0.604	

Table 2. Comparison on WTH, Weather, ILI, and Exchange datasets

To compare our results to the outcome of the complex models we added the MSE and MAE values for the best performing models for the different data sets. For ETTh1, ETTh2, and ETTm1 the best complex model is SCINet. In case of ECL different complex models showed the best results for different horizon, but for the majority of cases Informer performed the best. To keep the comparison table simple, we only show the result for Informer in case of ECL. For WTH data the Informer model was performing always the best, and for the remaining data sets Autoformer showed the best performance. In Table 3 and 4 the results for these complex models are given.

Dataset		ETTh1					ETTh2					ETTm1					ECL				
Horizon		24	48	168	336	720	24	48	168	336	720	24	48	96	288	672	48	168	336	720	960
SCINet	MSE	0.341	0.368	0.451	0.502	0.583	0.188	0.279	0.505	0.618	1.074	0.126	0.169	0.191	0.365	0.713	0.269	0.300	0.311	0.308	0.328
	MAE	0.379	0.395	0.457	0.497	0.560	0.288	0.358	0.504	0.560	0.761	0.229	0.274	0.291	0.415	0.604	0.351	0.376	0.385	0.385	0.406

Table 3. Results of best complex model on ETTh1, ETTh2, ETTm1, and ECL

Dataset		WTH					Weather					ILI				Exchange			
Horizon		24	48	168	336	720	96	192	336	720	24	36	48	60	96	192	336	720	
Informer for WTH	MSE	0.355	0.471	0.613	0.626	0.680	0.266	0.307	0.359	0.419	3.484	3.103	2.669	2.770	0.197	0.300	0.509	1.447	
Autoformer for rest	MAE	0.383	0.456	0.544	0.548	0.569	0.336	0.367	0.395	0.428	1.287	1.148	1.085	1.125	0.323	0.369	0.524	0.941	

Table 4. Results of best complex model on WTH, Weather, ILI, and Exchange datasets

As visible the performance based on MSE and MAE is in general for the complex models the best, when comparing it to our results in Table 1 and 2. For many data sets the difference in performance is severe. But for the Weather and Exchange data set the linear regression based on our reproduced values performs better. According to one of the original sources Zhou et al. [2] most machine learning methods outperform ARIMA in an univariate setting. This is clearly visible in our comparison. This fact raised already doubts concerning the results in the multivariate setting of the original paper when we read it the first time. Without going into details of the data structure (e.g., presence of a trend) of the Weather and Exchange data set we cannot explain why the performance of the linear regression is the best. A follow-up research study would be needed.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study we tried to reproduce the outcome of the research paper "Do Simpler Statistical Methods Perform Better in Multivariate Long Sequence Time-Series Forecasting?" [3]. As we had the original code available for the linear regression part we were able to generate the exact numbers. Without that we would not have been successful, because of the unprecise formulation of the benchmark model and lack of details in that paper. Furthermore, the implementation of the original article does not match with the description in that research paper. In our understanding the intention of the original article is very different to the implementation and therefore, we implemented it independently. As expected, our results differ severely from the outcome presented in the original paper. In line with other research outcomes (e.g., ARIMA performance in a univariate setting) we cannot conclude that simple models are better than recent deep learning methods in a multivariate long sequence time-series forecasting. Considering this outcome we were not able to reproduce the conclusion of the original paper.

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